

COMPETENCE-BASED APPROACH TO THE FORMATION OF A LINGUISTIC PERSONALITY IN THE LINGUOCULTURAL CONCEPT OF TEACHING THE RUSSIAN LANGUAGE

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7827439>

Annotation. The article reveals the main provisions of the concept, humanistic orientation and anthropocentric orientation, the basics of culturologically oriented textbooks implementing a competence-based approach to the formation of a linguistic personality. The focus is on linguistic and cultural competence (language acquisition in the dialogue of cultures) and related communicative, linguistic, and linguistic competencies.

Keywords: linguistic personality, linguoculturological concept, linguistic, linguistic, communicative, linguoculturological competence.

The concept of "linguistic personality" has reason to be considered one of the most frequent in the linguistic and linguodidactic scientific and methodological literature of the last decade. The interest in the concept of "linguistic personality" is due to:

- 1) the anthropocentric paradigm of linguistics (interest in a person as a native speaker, user and creator of a language);
- 2) the formation of integrated branches of linguistics in this regard: psycholinguistics, sociolinguistics, ethnolinguistics, linguoculturology;
- 3) increasing the theoretical level of linguodidactics, which has found its expression in the actualization of the concept of "linguistic education" along with the traditional terms "language teaching" or "language teaching";
- 4) increased demands of society for linguistic education – the study of the Russian language as the state and the language of interethnic communication, the new education standards proclaim as a necessary element of the meta-subject competencies of a person of culture (general cultural, professional thinking competencies) and subject skills (the ability to read, write, perceive the world, communicate in the language being studied).

The problem of the formation of a linguistic personality is given great attention in linguistic and linguodidactic research [1]. The essence of the linguoculturological concept in a brief summary is as follows:

1. The central, system-forming concept is the concept of "Linguistic personality". The formation of a linguistic personality is proclaimed as the main goal of teaching the Russian language, and its real communicative, cognitive and cultural needs form the basis of the learning system.
2. The acquisition of a second language involves the acquisition of a new linguistic picture of the world. This is a concept it is the key and reflects the cognitive function of language, the first stage of which is the way of nominating (naming) objects of the surrounding reality. To know the linguistic picture of the world of the language being studied means to be imbued with the worldview of the people.

3. Awareness of language as a cultural phenomenon, as a cultural and historical environment embodying the history, culture, customs of the people, comprehension of language as a treasury of culture leads to the need to describe the national and cultural component of the meanings of linguistic units at all levels and, above all, vocabulary, phraseology, aphorisms and text. The formation of the ethno-cultural competence of students based on this material is the most important component of the content of teaching the Russian language in technical universities.

4. A single linguistic and cultural space, national-Russian bilingualism (bilingualism), a multilingual linguistic personality, a dialogue of cultures are natural concepts in a multilingual educational space.

5. The linguistic picture of the world, the national-cultural halo of the word is especially vividly reflected in the key words-concepts, words-images and symbols.

6. Mastering the norms of speech communication, developing communicative competence is one of the goals of teaching Russian in universities, to achieve which it is necessary to describe the national and cultural characteristics of speech behavior, rules of intercultural communication.

Experience of theoretical substantiation and development of the linguocultural concept of teaching the Russian language, its educational and methodological support (textbooks, elective course, dictionaries, special courses), the organization of experimental training, the process of training students and teachers in the system of university and additional education, evaluation of the results achieved and at the same time discussion of ways to improve the methodological system of formation of linguistic and cultural competence of students in conjunction with other competencies on the basis of further enrichment of the content and technology of training The Russian language is presented in the monograph by Prof. L. G. Sayakhova [2].

In the triad of the initial concepts of the linguocultural concept of teaching the Russian language: man, language, culture – the central place is occupied by the concept of man. A person is both a linguistic and cultural personality: language and culture meet and interact in a person. The central, system-forming concept of the linguoculturological concept of language teaching is the concept of "linguistic personality", the formation of which is proclaimed as the main goal of linguoculturological concepts of teaching the Russian language.

In the conditions of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the task of forming a multilingual (at least trilingual) personality is set: language personality based on the native language, enriching it with knowledge of Russian as the state language and the language of interethnic communication, one of the world languages, knowledge of one (two) foreign languages. The development of a linguistic personality is associated with the formation of its competencies: linguistic (practical knowledge of the language), linguistic (theoretical knowledge of the language), communicative (using the language in accordance with the goals and communication situation, skills of correct speech conduct), culturological (entering the culture of the language being studied, overcoming the cultural barrier in communication).

The concept of "linguistic personality" is based on the concept of personality as a subject of relations and conscious activity, determined by this system of social relations, culture and also conditioned by its biological characteristics.

The "linguistic personality" as such does not begin at the level of ordinary linguistic semantics (possession of an elementary dictionary and grammar is the zero, verbal-associative level),

but at the cognitive level characterizing the knowledge of the world embodied in language, i.e. the linguistic picture of the world and the thesaurus of personality and further at the motivational, pragmatic level, covering the communicative-the activity needs of the individual and its intentional sphere [4].

Language teaching is built in accordance with the content of the concept of language and its main functions. Distinguish: language in general (representation about a single human language) and the language of a given people, i.e. an ethnic language. Language is:

1) A historically developed sign system that serves as a means of communication, thinking and cognition; a means of creating, storing and transmitting information. 2) Speech, language ability. The gift of speech. 3) A set of means of expression in verbal creativity, style (Pushkin's language. The language of science). In accordance with the content of the concept of "language", students should learn common phenomena inherent in all languages (the origin and development of language, its social nature, connection with thinking, system structure, language and speech, language functions: cognitive, thinking, communicative, influencing, emotive, aesthetic, cumulative) and specific features of a particular language being studied. It is assumed: 1. Study language as a sign system (structure and laws of language functioning). 2. Development of language ability, teaching speech communication. 3. The study of language in the stylistic aspect and as the primary element of fiction. [5]

In the linguodidactic aspect, the interrelated study of language and culture can be interpreted as follows. Language acquisition there is a simultaneous assimilation of native culture or entry into the culture of the people-the carrier of the studied language. The communicative principle of language teaching actualizes this problem, because language communication is a necessary condition for the existence and development of human culture, ensuring the unity of cultural processes within this community: the creation, storage and transfer of cultural values. In the linguistic and cultural concept of teaching speech communication, the general didactic and psychological principles of a developmental and activity-based approach to learning, the provisions of the psycholinguistic theory of speech communication are combined ideas of communicative-pragmatic and functional-semantic linguistics, linguistics of the text, ideas of the formation of a linguistic personality. Anthropocentric orientation of modern linguodidactics, setting on the formation of language personality as the main goal linguistic education led to the idea of a competence-based approach. [7]

The term "competence" was introduced by N. Chomsky, who laid the foundations of the theory of generative grammars and the theory of formal languages.

When studying a non-native language, the picture is somewhat different: language learning begins most often with a conscious assimilation of the language structure. The role of linguistic knowledge about the levels and units of language is fundamental here: the process of practical language acquisition is carried out in parallel with the assimilation of linguistic knowledge about the rules of its construction and functioning. The essence of linguistic competence is the formation of a holistic view of the subject area "Russian language" as a linguistic discipline with its own system of scientific concepts and terms. The psychological foundations of speech development are revealed by the theory of speech activity. Speech teaching in modern psycholinguistics is understood as teaching foreign language material (means of communication) and communication activities. Speech activity is carried out primarily on the basis of knowledge of the language system, which, being fixed in the human mind, provides understanding and production of speech. "Language competence is the ability

to understand and produce an unlimited number of linguistically correct sentences with the help of learned language signs and their rules connections. Discursive competence is the ability to connect sentences into a coherent message using various syntactic and lexical means. [8]

Scientific and methodological prerequisites for the idea of forming linguistic and cultural competence – (the dynamics of the development of the problem "Language and culture" as the philosophical basis of the linguistic and cultural concept, the anthropocentric paradigm of linguistics with its interest in man and his communicative and cultural needs. As a possible basis for the implementation of the formation of linguistic and cultural competence of a linguistic personality, we present the content of the textbook "The Russian language in the dialogue of cultures" Elective course [3].

V. V. Vorobyov, L. G. Sayakhova. Elective course "Russian language in the dialogue of cultures". The main goals and objectives of the elective course:

- description of language as a treasure trove of culture; disclosure of the national-cultural component of the meanings of linguistic units of different levels: vocabulary, phraseology, text, grammar;
- consideration of language as an indicator of a person's culture, the culture of his speech and communication, including intercultural
- development of ways to form and develop a linguistic personality capable of intercultural communication.

Note that the division of the process of forming a linguistic personality on competence is purely conditional, but it is advisable to draw attention to each of them. In reality, the formation of a linguistic personality is an integral process in which these competencies are interrelated and inseparable. [6]

Comparative aspect: difficulties of studying the Russian language by students of a technical university due to the different structure of languages (Russian as inflectional, the formation of words in, the presence of prefixes in them, differences in grammatical categories: the presence of the category of the genus of nouns, types of verbs, features of the language), the case system of nouns, phrases. All of the above develops linguistic thinking of students, helps conscious language learning on a theoretical basis.

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